

Privacy Policy

1. Responsible

The Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure - European Research Infrastructure Consortium (hereinafter “MIRRI-ERIC”) is a legal entity set up by the Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/1204 of 16 June 2022.

MIRRI-ERIC is the data controller for the purpose of this Privacy Policy and its identification and location data are:

Name: Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure - European Research Infrastructure Consortium “MIRRI-ERIC”

Address: University of Minho, Campus of Gualtar, Pedagogic Complex 3, Floor 0, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal

Institutional email: info@mirri.org

Email for issues related to this Privacy Policy: info@mirri.org

2. Application scope and object of the Privacy Policy

MIRRI-ERIC is fully committed to respecting people's privacy. To ensure the application of the fundamental right to the protection of personal data, MIRRI-ERIC has adopted this basic policy of data protection, which is based on the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (EU GDPR) and applies to any website within the domain "mirri.org", the official institutional webportal of MIRRI-ERIC.

The MIRRI-ERIC webportal is hosted at the servers of the Universitat de València (hereinafter “UV”), the institution co-hosting the Central Coordinating Unit of MIRRI-ERIC in Spain. Therefore, UV is a processor of your personal data according to the definition of the EU GDPR.

The main aim of this privacy policy is to inform the users on the way personal data are collected and processed, providing relevant information to them, as well as fixing the accessing conditions and the use of the MIRRI-ERIC webportal regarding privacy.

Nevertheless, specific or complementary privacy policies can be established in certain websites or resources/applications contained in the MIRRI-ERIC webportal, which due to its specificity require so. Without prejudice to adjust to the principles included in this privacy policy, the user will have to verify the conditions which rule personal data processing at:

- a) Contact mailboxes
- b) Specific set procedures for the collecting of personal data (e.g., TNA applications)

Legal bases and purposes of the processing operations - processed data- storage duration MIRRI-ERIC informs the users that it can collect any personal data facilitated as a consequence of the access and/or usage of the MIRRI-ERIC webportal and related services, as well as mailings or through personal contacts and business cards.

In general, the collected data can be used with administrative, statistical, scientific, researching, and cultural and divulging aims, and to attend to your queries, suggestions and complaints. In any case, the specific use will always be adjusted to the objectives for which the data were collected.

In particular, MIRRI-ERIC processes personal data for the following purposes:

Purpose	Legal basis	Processed personal data	Storage duration
Participation in the forum of experts on the basis of the on Terms of use	Consent given by the data subject MIRRI webportal Terms and conditions of use	Forum user's: - Name - Surname - Employing organization - Position - E-mail address	Until withdrawal of the consent
Communicate about MIRRI-ERIC and its activities (e.g., Newsletter) and answer	Consent given by the data Subject	Contact's: - Name - Surname - E-mail address - Exchange of emails	No longer than necessary for the purpose for which it was processed or

questions and inquires of the data subject		through the contact form and exchanging Messages - Meta data that may or may not be related to the e-mail of the data subject	until withdrawal of the consent.
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3. Lawfulness

MIRRI-ERIC processes users' personal data to fulfill its mission in the public interest, as well as to fulfill the legal obligations applicable to MIRRI-ERIC, to perform contracts to which the data subject is a party or when the purpose of the processing requires the user's consent, which must be realized by a clear affirmative action.

4. Data disclosures

The personal information provided by users may be communicated to third parties in the cases set out in the EU GDPR and its enforcing regulations, in all cases demanding the consent of users when needed.

MIRRI-ERIC publishes data on its webportal in the following cases:

a) Governance and organisation

MIRRI-ERIC has available on its websites the contact details of the people working in the Central Coordinating Unit and participating in the different governing bodies. Usually, this information is in the section "Governance & People" of the webportal. The purpose of these data is exclusively to provide contact information within the context of the specific functions and competences of MIRRI-ERIC.

In specific cases, the email address may be excluded from the public lists or replaced by a new one when there is a justified cause, and particularly when required to protect the person's personal information. To make such this request please contact info@mirri.org

b) Publications

MIRRI-ERIC may also publish personal data (name, surname, position) when the partners or the users participate in any selective or competitive processes related with MIRRI-ERIC, in accordance with the applicable regulations.

The use of the data published on the official webportal of MIRRI-ERIC will be related exclusively to the purposes described in this Privacy Policy. Their use will be prohibited for any other purpose and particularly, for commercial or advertising purposes.

Infringements of this provision will result in the notification of the facts to the Portuguese Data Protection Authority or to other enforcement authorities, without prejudice to the exercise of other applicable legal actions by MIRRI-ERIC.

5. Data storage

The provided personal data will be stored no longer than necessary to fulfil the purpose for which they are obtained and to determine the possible responsibilities deriving from the purpose, in addition to the periods established in applicable laws. However, MIRRI-ERIC may storage them for longer periods provided they are processed exclusively for archival purposes in the public interest, scientific and historical research purposes, or statistical purposes. In such cases, MIRRI-ERIC is committed to apply the appropriate technical and organisational measures imposed by the EU GDPR.

6. Accuracy (Data Quality)

Users guarantee the authenticity and accuracy of the data and information supplied pursuant to the use of the MIRRI-ERIC webportal. Any false or inaccurate information or data provided, as well as the damage this information might cause, will be the responsibility of the users. Therefore, users are obliged to maintain their information and data updated so they conform to reality at any time and they commit to communicate, as soon as possible, modifications related to their personal data, as well as corrections of inaccurate data.

Also, in the event that the personal data registered is wholly or partly inaccurate or incomplete, MIRRI-ERIC will proceed to their cancellation or substitution by the corresponding rectified or completed data, without prejudice to the powers granted to data subjects in the article 16 of the EU GDPR.

MIRRI-ERIC will take all necessary measures to ensure that the data provided are maintained correctly, without alterations.

7. Confidentiality and security

The personal data collected by MIRRI-ERIC will be treated in such a way as to adequately guarantee its security and confidentiality, applying the appropriate technical and organisational measures to minimize possible risks.

In case the processing of personal data is outsourced to a third party, MIRRI-ERIC will conclude a written agreement with this third party ensuring that the processor provides the necessary safeguards in accordance with the GDPR.

8. Sending of emails

The emails sent from a MIRRI-ERIC account (name.surname@mirri.org or function@mirri.org) aim to serve the purposes of the infrastructure. By default, its content is considered confidential and its reproduction or distribution without express authorisation is not allowed, unless required by the nature or content of the message.

The content of emails sent to a MIRRI-ERIC account could be visible by the Universitat de València and MIRRI-ERIC staff other than the addressee, with the exclusive purpose of properly carrying out the attention service to our users.

Additionally, sending emails to MIRRI-ERIC accounts is subjected to our conditions of use and our privacy policies. Any use contrary to our conditions and policies, particularly the improper disclosure of confidential content, the unauthorised collection of data or spamming could lead to legal actions by MIRRI-ERIC.

Any incident related to the reception of our emails and particularly those regarding safety and confidentiality, shall be communicated to web@mirri.org.

The MIRRI-ERIC's email addresses are published on the website for scientific and administrative purposes only. The use of these addresses for any other purpose, and in particular for commercial purposes or mass mailing (SPAM), will be considered contrary to the legality and purpose limitation principles of the EU GDPR.

9. Minors and persons under legal guardianship

In general terms, the MIRRI-ERIC webportal is not aimed to provide services to minors nor the compilation of their data. In any case, the contents shown, being contents related to microbiological science, are suitable for people of any age.

In those cases, in which personal data of minors is processed, the provisions of their specific privacy policies will apply, bearing in mind that minors under 14 years of age should not provide their personal data without the prior consent of their parents or guardians.

Users legally incapacitated by virtue of a judicial resolution that requires the consent of their legal guardians for the processing of their personal information have the obligation to provide the appropriate authorisation.

10. User rights

MIRRI-ERIC is fully adapted to the EU GDPR and, therefore, has an address web@mirri.org for any information, suggestions, requests for the exercise of rights and the amicable resolution of disputes regarding the protection of personal data.

Any person may exercise the following rights over the files owned by MIRRI-ERIC, in the terms established by the EU GDPR:

- a) Right of access to your personal data and to know which ones are being processed and the processing operations carried out with them.
- b) Right to correct any inaccurate data.
- c) Right to delete your personal data.
- d) Right to object or limit to the processing of your personal data.
- e) Right to data portability.
- f) Right to revoke your consent at any time.

Users can exercise their rights, when appropriate, before MIRRI-ERIC - University of Minho, Campus of Gualtar, Pedagogic Complex 3, Floor 0, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal, info@mirri.org.

However, it is recommended to request our friendly dispute resolution service for data protection and new technologies through web@mirri.org, before making any complaint,

in the event of a suspected breach of this privacy policy. The use of this service will, in no case, prejudice user's right to contact the Portuguese Data Protection Authority.

11. Third Party Sites

On the MIRRI-ERIC webportal the users can find links that lead them to external, third-party websites. Once users access these links, the present Privacy Policy will cease to have effect and users will be subject to the specific privacy policy of the third-party website. Consequently, MIRRI-ERIC disclaims all liability related to the processing of data by these websites and recommends users to read carefully their privacy policies.